

Artículo de investigación

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Orientación vocacional del estudiante en el liceo de talento deportivo municipio Independencia, estado Yaracuy

Vocational orientation of the student in the high school of sports talent in the municipality of Independence, Yaracuy state

Orientação vocacional do aluno no liceu de talentos desportivos do município de Independência, estado de Yaracuy

Resumen

El presente artículo estuvo enmarcado en la temática: orientación vocacional y su línea de investigación fundamentos y praxis de la orientación, el cual tuvo como propósito develar el proceso de orientación vocacional del estudiante en el LICEO DE TALENTO DEPORTIVO, desde el punto de vista metodológico correspondió a una investigación cualitativa de campo, se estudió una situación real refiriéndose a un diseño y método fenomenológico con entrevista a profundidad, se recopiló la información pertinente de cuatro informantes clave que mostraron cualidades para redescubrir la situación existente; apoyados en teóricos. Se aplicó técnica e instrumento como: entrevista a profundidad, la observación directa, que permitió la información necesaria en función de visualizar la realidad existente; dicho instrumento constó de 6 preguntas abiertas aplicado a estos sujetos clave del mencionado liceo. Se recopiló toda la información y se procedió al análisis e interpretación de los resultados empleando la triangulación de fuentes teóricas e informantes que permitieron las reflexiones finales desde el fenómeno estudiado. Se concluyó que, la orientación vocacional no se da debidamente en la institución deportiva ya que la orientadora, entrenadores y docentes académicos no toman en cuenta las habilidades, competencias de los jóvenes, se comprendió la importancia el conocerse internamente siendo partícipes conscientes de su decisión, lograr buenos avances

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significativos en lo que a orientación vocacional se refiere, así el estudiante podía identificar sus aptitudes, habilidades, intereses y capacidades, para que tome la decisión que cambie su proyección de vida.

Palabras clave: Epistemología, ontología, orientación.

Abstract

The present article is framed within the theme of vocational orientation and its research foundations and praxis within the context of student guidance at LICEO DE TALENTO DEPORTIVO. The purpose is to elucidate the process of vocational orientation for students. Methodologically, this study employs a qualitative field research approach, focusing on a real-life situation using a phenomenological design and method, incorporating in-depth interviews with four key informants identified for their ability to provide insights into the existing situation. The data collection techniques include in-depth interviews and direct observation, aimed at gathering necessary information to comprehend the current reality. The interview protocol consists of six open-ended questions administered to the selected participants from the aforementioned high school. Following data collection, the information was meticulously compiled and subjected to analysis and interpretation. This involved triangulation of data from both theoretical sources and informants, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study. The findings reveal inadequacies in the provision of vocational guidance within the sports institution, attributable to the oversight of counselors, coaches, and academic teachers in considering the individual skills and competencies of students. The study underscores the significance of self-awareness and active participation in decision-making processes, emphasizing the pivotal role these play in effective vocational guidance. Consequently, fostering such awareness can lead to meaningful progress in assisting students to identify their aptitudes, interests, and abilities, thereby empowering them to make informed decisions that positively impact their future trajectories.

Key words: Epistemology, ontology, orientation.

Resumo

O presente artigo foi enquadrado na temática: orientação vocacional e sua linha de investigação fundamentos e práxis da orientação, que teve como objetivo desvelar o processo de orientação vocacional do aluno no LICEU DE TALENTO DEPORTIVO, do ponto de vista metodológico correspondeu a uma investigação qualitativa de campo, foi estudada uma situação real referente a um desenho e método fenomenológico com entrevista em profundidade, foi compilada a informação pertinente de quatro informantes chaves que mostraram qualidades para redescobrir a situação existente; apoiados em teóricos. A técnica e o instrumento aplicados foram: entrevista em profundidade, observação direta, que permitiu a obtenção das informações necessárias para visualizar a realidade existente; esse instrumento consistiu em 6 perguntas abertas aplicadas a esses sujeitos-chave da escola de ensino médio mencionada. Todas as informações foram compiladas e procedeu-se à análise e interpretação dos resultados utilizando a triangulação de fontes

teóricas e informantes que permitiram as reflexões finais do fenômeno estudado. Concluiu-se que a orientação vocacional não é dada adequadamente na instituição esportiva porque o orientador, os treinadores e os professores acadêmicos não levam em conta as habilidades e competências dos jovens, entendeu-se a importância de se conhecer internamente, sendo participantes conscientes de sua decisão, alcançando um bom progresso significativo no que diz respeito à orientação vocacional, para que o aluno possa identificar suas aptidões, habilidades, interesses e capacidades, para tomar a decisão de mudar sua projeção de vida.

Palavras-chave: Epistemologia, ontologia, orientação.

Introduction and Background

The objective of the study was to discover the process of vocational orientation in the students of the Liceo de Talento Deportivo Municipio Independencia, Yaracuy state, a step that went into the reality and daily experiences of the individuals, revealing its unforeseen effectiveness. The exploration was carried out within the framework of the research of the Universidad Pedagógica Experimental Libertador (UPEL) under the thematic area of Vocational Guidance, specifically in the domain of Foundations and Praxis of Guidance. The role of the guidance counselor has undergone a series of changes as a guide/supporter of adolescents, including adaptations to the new educational reforms, a challenging task in the midst of social changes derived from family, political, economic and socio-educational aspects.

The unwritten history of guidance traces back to magical-religious origins, closely linked to astronomy, as indicated by Martínez and Quintanal-Téllez (2002). Leadership roles were attributed to priests, sorcerers, emperors, pharaohs, princes, and national leaders, who attributed individual behavior to celestial position and prescribed societal norms and labor based on astrological configurations and divine ordinances.

The earliest documented instances of guidance are found in ancient Greece and Rome, where the states promoted conditions to train their citizens in appropriate professions with capabilities of their social class to which they belonged. In this order of ideas and context Plato (347d.C.) "should be seen as the driving force of the first attempts to codify directions in function of school use and in the specific capacity of the soul" (p.18).

Aristotle, as cited by Aguilar (1982), discussed the development of rationality in the choice of occupation based on individuals' interests, advocating not for a promotion of free choice or change regarding what man can do on earth, but rather for a decision to live fully; there was no possibility of changing destiny, but rather of living abundantly. The philosopher did not employ the term "vocation" or the concept of a calling to perform one profession or another, nor did he propose the existence of free initiative in life, as Plato, as referenced by Martínez (2002), projected.

However, Aristotle, as referenced by Aguilar (1982), did address how to carry out any profession, which did involve a personal decision; the freedom of choice lay in deciding, once the supreme good was known, and exercising it within the profession, meaning that freedom pertained to how to carry out activities.

Vocational guidance originated in the United States through the work of Frank Parsons (1908), who established the first agency aimed at assisting young individuals in career decision-making, with its roots in Boston. The challenge was to place individuals in the most suitable positions through guidance, considering their personal interests. The ultimate goals were the integration of individuals into society, so counseling endeavored to explore the aptitudes of individuals, taking into account personal, economic, and social conditions, aiming for professions that would yield better outcomes.

In this context, Parsons (cited) narrated how he assisted individuals in their work. His study consisted of three parts: A) Identifying talents, abilities, interests, resources, limitations, and characteristics, and clearly defining objectives. B) Understanding the prerequisites for success, advantages, disadvantages, compensations, opportunities, and prospects of different career paths. C) Comparing the aforementioned points.

Following these assertions, Super (1953), in his theory of "development of self-concept," suggested that "when the individual had decided on a vocation, it was imperative to have understood one's childhood and life process, to determine how the self-concept was manifested, and for the individual to engage in one activity over another" (p. 38).

In addition to the above, Super (cited) delineated four vocational stages: A) Development, spanning from birth to adolescence, during which individuals acquire skills, merits, and inclinations towards their characterization through the environments they inhabit. B) Exploration, encompassing ages 15 to 24, the phase marked by deep introspection, affirmation, and confrontation with discoveries from the previous phase, along with the emergence of professional preferences. It is further subdivided into temporal periods: adolescence, characterized by the assimilation of skills, merits, and inclinations, gradually leading to novel behaviors and

the honing of perceived talents and competencies; and the transformation period from adolescence to maturity, aiming towards vocational preferences.

Continuing with the stages, C) Establishment, spans from ages 25 to 44, where individuals explore various paths to achieve balance in their occupations across different facets of life; D) Decline, starting from age 65, where physical and intellectual conditions begin to wane, new roles emerge, many retire and pursue other activities, often returning to family and home.

Vocational development, as perceived by Super (cited), was an inseparable declaration of personal progress, reflecting a transformation throughout the individual's life cycle, meaning vocational engagement evolves progressively based on one's current phase (Pereira, 2015). Furthermore, evaluating an individual entails considering all qualities and conditions in their vocational maturity. Castellano (2007) remarked that an individual is vocally fruitful when there is alignment between vocational actions and chronological age.

Holland's theory (1959) of career choice or occupational preference inventory represented a synthesis of two schools of thought in work psychology. His overarching perspective was the subsequent development of the career choice hypothesis as an extension of personality and an attempt to fully realize an individual's behavioral style within the context of their work life.

An innovative feature he introduced was the notion that individuals reflect their desired work environments onto the world of work. Rather than allowing stereotypes to confound individuals, Holland (cited) guided the process of belief formation and considered individuals' work experiences as dogmas based on reality. In his initial statements, he posited that there existed a limited number of societal work environments, such as: realistic (doers), including tasks that involve physical skills, precise challenges, and professions like laborers, aviation, technicians, and sculptors; social (helpers), prioritizing interpersonal relationships, avoiding situations requiring scientific activity or extensive physical skills; investigative (thinkers), preferring rational thought and behavior, avoiding personal contact, often being precise, analytical, and systematic.

In this conceptual framework, the hierarchical evolution of work environments was represented by individual adaptations to six

work environments. A) Realistic individuals (doers); impulsive individuals who excel in tasks requiring physical skills, precise challenges, professions including laborers, aviation, technicians, and sculptors. B) Social individuals (helpers); prioritizing interpersonal relationships, avoiding situations requiring scientific activity or extensive physical skills. C) Investigative individuals (thinkers); preferring rational thought and behavior, avoiding personal contact, often being precise, analytical, and systematic. D) Conventional individuals (organizers); highly dominant, equating power with social status, exploring careers such as shareholders, managers, statisticians, accountants, and administrators. E) Enterprising individuals (persuaders); adept in verbal persuasion, experiencing power and social status, typically wholesalers, state legislators, providers. F) Artistic individuals (creators); emotionally inclined individuals such as poets, musicians, dramatists, and sculptors, engaging in artistic expression, yet exhibiting limited self-control, introversion, and social aloofness.

In Venezuela, vocational guidance has been closely linked with education, its historical trajectory marked by various phases corresponding to changes dictated by state policies. During the first decade of the 21st century, Venezuelan education underwent transformations aimed at a new conception of humanity, emphasizing inclusivity that respects and recognizes diversity and considers human continuity from conception to death.

From a qualitative perspective, inquiry into vocational areas encompassed different reference points: vocational groups (specific, occupational), profession, intentionality, socialization, co-determination, or the teaching and learning process, and vocational information. It is noteworthy that sports activities have significant educational potential for youth, contributing to educational, occupational, professional, physical, mental, emotional, and social placements.

During adolescence, there are social exchanges in search of independence and identity; hence, sports practice has been of great relevance for the acquisition of values and necessary skills in young individuals. From the researcher's standpoint, adolescents who engage in sports experience health benefits in adulthood; physical exercise aids in better rest, quality sleep, tension release, relaxation, motor coordination, endurance,

muscular strength, flexibility, combating obesity, fostering effort appreciation, and learning to strive for short-, medium-, and long-term goals. Consequently, sports promote consistency, discipline, emotional stability, increased self-esteem, well-being, and optimism. Positive mood states encourage tackling challenges with a different attitude, aiding in personality development.

According to research conducted at the TALENTO DEPORTIVO educational center, adolescents have undergone physical-sporting tests in various disciplines including chess, basketball, table tennis, judo, archery, swimming, athletics, weightlifting, volleyball, taekwondo, karate, fencing, baseball, wrestling, gymnastics, futsal, and field football. These Olympic sports are projected to serve as the sports reserve for the Yaracuy state in the future.

This recruitment process has allowed for their engagement and sporting preparation under the guidance of counselors and coaches, who must enhance attitudes and aptitudes in each individual. Student athletes do not isolate themselves from their academic preparation; they simultaneously fulfill their school obligations and receive annual induction talks from academic teachers, sports coordinators, counselors, and school management. These talks inform them of institutional norms and the aspects they must adhere to as student athletes, aligning with the institutional vision-mission of talent recruitment to maintain an athletic reserve for school, national, Paralympic, and Olympic games.

It should be noted that, despite these processes of sports training and academic induction, other student peculiarities have arisen. These include pupils influenced by sporting parents, pupils who have experienced vicarious learning, pupils attracted by being idle adolescents or pupils who possess innate aptitudes and qualities but lack vocational, academic and sporting guidance. Various characteristics are not addressed in a timely manner, causing the athletic potential of most of these young people to dissipate. Therefore, students in the sports high school do not receive adequate vocational guidance and the institution does not apply dedicated methods for this purpose. At present, only interviews are conducted, which lack essential elements for sports choice; therefore, vocational counseling is necessary for sports high school students.

In this context, contributions and/or interpretations regarding vocational disposition are requested, as there currently lacks an innovative academic guidance program that enables comprehensive engagement with these active young individuals within the sports school environment. Consequently, the following questions arise: What is the process of vocational guidance for students at the Yaracuy Sports Talent High School? What are the epistemological, ontological, axiological, and methodological foundations of vocational guidance provided to students at the Yaracuy Sports Talent High School? What reflection does the vocational guidance offered to students at the Yaracuy Sports Talent High School in the Municipio Independencia, Yaracuy State, provoke?

Significance

According to Molina (2001), mentoring is a social practice aimed at implementing processes of human development as epistemic subjects across the dimensions of existence, living, serving, knowing, and acting within personal, familial, or community contexts throughout life, with the objective of developing skills and giving rise to processes of self-definition or liberation in the ongoing construction for the holistic well-being of those who have created and transformed their knowledge from specific contexts, physical, biological, social, and/or economic realities. This entails the formative development of young people, enabling them to make decisions at a given moment, to act to clarify doubts and values, taking into account economic and educational conditions.

The pedagogical relevance of the research lay in the processes of young athletes identifying their personal goals, being autonomous and self-sufficient in recognizing their potentialities or clarifying their needs and/or aspirations while balancing their personal and professional aims. Guidance has represented assistance by providing self-knowledge regarding capacities, skills, and aptitudes for future career choices.

Regarding methodological relevance, hermeneutic phenomenology was applied to bolster the configuration of qualitative research, providing narratives capable of guiding the handling of the variable under study, as well as the significance of vocational guidance in students of the Talent Sports High School, Municipio

Independencia, Yaracuy State. Social relevance optimized the vocation of student athletes at the Talent Sports High School in improving the quality of their choices.

The technical tool employed in decision-making focused to guide the educational-sporting process and foster individual-collective work. In this conceptual framework, it was estimated that from a theoretical standpoint, the research facilitated the generation of a referential framework of knowledge and wisdom to guide explanatory constructions regarding the understanding of the meaning of vocational guidance for students at the Talent Sports High School in the Municipio Independencia, Yaracuy State.

In practical terms, it constituted the starting point with tools for change for counselors, academic teachers, and sports coaches, allowing them to understand the meaning of guidance, consider alternatives to guide student athletes at the sports high school and other educational institutions, through adapted models tailored to the particular characteristics of each individual. The ultimate purpose of guidance in its educational process was the autonomous and independent development, intellectual, emotional, and behavioral, of individuals in managing their personal affairs and social responsibilities.

Furthermore, the analysis and reflection on the meaning of the theoretical factors of the researched theme and its development in educational practice led to methodological contributions in terms of contrasting normative doctrinal discourse with the evidence found in the institution under study. This analysis and reflection on the meaning of the theoretical factors of the researched theme and its development in educational practice led to methodological contributions in terms of contrasting normative doctrinal discourse with the evidence found in the institution under study.

Methodology

The methodological approach of the research led to the onto-epistemic dimension, a procedure that systematically allowed for contrasting, confirming, rejecting, constructing, and interpreting the nature of the object under study. In this regard, the operational technical aspects guided by the

phenomenological method served for data processing, in addition to imparting scientific rigor to the study.

Regarding the ontological aspect, Hiernaux (2010) indicated that, due to its essential characteristics, the ontology underpinning the present inquiry is humanism, a term rooted in classical antiquity, which over the centuries has been imbued with new contents. For the Sophists, it signifies "the idea of human formation," which is related to the so-called "general human" education. In philosophy, it is the movement of the Renaissance aimed at elevating the dignity of the human spirit. The man of the Renaissance humanists was the possessor of riches and the power of the wise.

Derived from the foregoing, it is indisputable that the study promoted humanism as an essential dimension, as the central interest was to reflect on the vocational guidance of students at the Talent Sports High School in the Municipio Independencia, Yaracuy State. In this sense, from an ontological dimension, realities existed in the form of social constructions based on experience and/or social dynamics, of a local-specific nature of the key informants, depending on their form and content that kept them within the groups to which they belonged. Therefore, in the process of constructing knowledge of the key informants, it was supported by Burr's stance (1995), reality was constructed or emerged from interaction, social construction of interrelation, and subjectivities in a time-space framework.

The hermeneutic epistemological stance constituted aspects of reality that led to the necessary epistemological reflection for subjective or intersubjective construction grounded in the reality of which the subject was aware, recognizing oneself and the historical experiential context in which they were immersed. As pointed out by Morales (2011). On the epistemological level, knowledge was acquired and communicated by the key informants regarding interpreting the pedagogical support approach in the planning of school activities; that is, investigating how they created, modified, and interpreted their experience and conceptions, supported by subjectivism and the socio-critical paradigm, as it created independence between the researcher and the object of research.

This epistemological dimension allowed for the attainment of knowledge legitimacy through the coherence of intersubjectively

interpreted facts, thereby contributing propositions to the considered thematic. The participants in the study; constituted by the narrators of the exploration: researcher, particular person, or groups of people involved with the investigated phenomenon. Object of study, through sensory perception see, hear, touch, and through other phenomena: believe, intuit, imagine, feel, anticipate. Data generation; flows through the versions expressed by the study participants, then analyzed, interpreted, and described. Reflective analysis. Signifying being alert and sensitive to being open to the meaning of the experiences recounted and written. The development of theory allowed for the written comprehension of the phenomenon under study and then interpretations.

In this sense, the search for vocational guidance experiences of students at the Talent Sports High School was not simply about understanding the individual cases treated or describing their particular characteristics but allowed for the elaboration of a scientifically valid or objective general conceptual structure of the same. Starting from the experiences or life-world of particular subjects, Husserl (1913) indicates that through consciousness, it is possible to construct a universal knowledge of the studied phenomenon.

To carry out the inquiry using this approach, one became acquainted with the concepts and principles of phenomenology and how to approach specific areas of study and mechanisms for seeking meanings. Experiences were known through narratives, stories, and attributions, essential because they admitted intuition, the nature of the dynamism of the environment, and even its evolution.

The contexts whose environments and structures were seen from partially outside, being the subject of study of other methods. Instead, the realities whose peculiar nature and structure have only been captured from the intrinsic frame of reference of the individual who lived and perceived them, demanding through the phenomenological method. For this reason, an "Objective" and "External" reality was not studied (as commonly considered) for all, but a fact whose attribute depended on how it is lived and observed by the individual; an internal and particular experience, magnified in each human being. It is for this reason that it cannot be introduced by impulse into the conceptual and methodical scheme pre-established by the researcher.

The present study was linked to qualitative research, under the phenomenological conception; which aimed at representing and interpreting the fundamental organizations of lived experience, as well as recognizing the meaning and pedagogical importance of such experiences according to Sandin cited in (Piñero and Rivera 2013), the researcher's stance was relevant to determining the relevance of studying the phenomenon. Consequently, it is important: The approach: was the general vision regarding man and the world that he brings to his work, making it scientific.

The participants in the study: constituted by the versions of the study, researcher, particular person, groups of people involved with the investigated phenomenon. Object of study: through sensory perception; seeing, hearing, touching, and through other phenomena: believing, intuiting, imagining, feeling, anticipating. Data generation: flowed through the versions expressed by the participants in the study, then it was analyzed, interpreted, and described. Reflective analysis: meant the search for a theme based on cognition and personal experience. The development of the theory: Allowed the written understanding of the phenomenon under study, then the interpretations, finally the understanding that was achieved in the recognition of the researcher's knowledge and the object of the research. The steps presented provided systematic rigor to present the phenomenon studied.

According to Martínez (2006), the informants represented the sample under study that provided criteria on the research phenomenon. Hence, for the collection of information, four (4) key informants were counted, that is, (01) counselor, (01) academic teacher, (01) sports teacher, (01) student of the institution under study who were referred to as informants 1, 2, 3, and 4, they provided relevant information from their particular experience in the institution and their connection with the theoretical possibilities of the object of study, the selection of the informants attending the Sports Talent High School of the Municipality Independencia, Yaracuy State. Based on the qualitative approach with the in-depth interview technique defined by Palella and Martins (2006).

In virtue of the qualitative approach, the interview script instrument was applied as defined by Buendía (2008) as "questions directed at social actors to seek what is important,

significant for the informants, discover events and subjective dimensions of individuals such as beliefs, thoughts, values" (p.159). Hence, the researcher became the interviewer of the facts that impact the phenomenon under study, therefore the interview was directed towards understanding the vocational orientation of the student at the Sports Talent High School in the Municipality of Independencia, Yaracuy State, whether in person or face-to-face with the key informants, with whom trust was initially established, informing them of the purpose of the study, the methodological perspective employed, and which aspects the interview comprised, as a mechanism to unite efforts to connect ideas and obtain relevant information that gave significance to the research. The resources used were the recorder and the video camera when necessary, with the approval of the interviewees.

Results

The results are presented through the responses obtained in the interviews, followed by the triangulation of information to subsequently arrive at an interpretation of the answers.

How is the process of vocational guidance towards the student of the Sports Talent High School conducted?

- 1. (Guidance Counselor):** Well, it's a process that goes hand in hand with the coach; if it's not done with the coach, we lose! Right! Because the coach is the one who will evaluate if that boy really has that vocation because... um... here we're not only talking about whether the boy is good at sports, we also go to the motivational part. For a boy to be successful in sports, he has to have motivation, he has to have skills, qualities, abilities. So, who discovers that? "The coach" because I can help them, I can train an athlete academically, and I can help him maintain his academic level, but I can't give him the sports skills to stay here. Right! Who has to evaluate those sports skills is the coach, and it is together with him that we can provide that guidance process so that the boy can be successful academically and in sports and achieve the objective of the sports talent units.

How do you promote vocational guidance towards students at the Sports Talent High School?

- 2. (Sports Coach):** I believe that the relationship between the coach and the athlete has to be ideal, exactly. We have to incorporate some element that perhaps we haven't taken into account so far to really know how far I can go in working with that kid and the result I can achieve.

What is your vocational preference?

- 3. (Student Athlete):** The sport? Which one? Basketball... I really like playing basketball, um... I don't know, since I started playing, this sport has caught my attention a lot, and thank God I have had many experiences, super good ones, that have given me the certainty or the security to say that I want to be a professional basketball player when I grow up... When did you decide to play basketball for the first time, what caught your attention? Um well, I don't really know... because, I didn't... before I started playing basketball, did the ball, the shoes, the court, the players catch your attention? I'd say everything, because obviously I entered, and I was a rookie, I didn't know how to dribble a ball, I didn't know how to make a pass, and damn, seeing people, teammates, how they did it, the movements they made, then what they achieved learning those things, already in this case would be... being in the state selection, representing the country, playing in world championships, South Americans, Olympics, even being professional and making a living through that (damn) I saw it... Damn, even I was going to practice "swimming" because I have a pathology in my back, and obviously a doctor told me that was the sport to adjust it (in quotes). Do you diagnose the student according to his or her sport discipline?

- 4. (Academic Teacher):** Yes, I always make my diagnosis; even at times, I start the first term, right! After that diagnosis, I set up, let's say, the planning, and during the term, something comes up that I couldn't detect in the previous diagnosis, in one case... and I take the general idea and make a diagnosis, perhaps orally or through a reading, and I can visualize another diagnosis.

Analysis: Hermeneusis

The ideal Vocational Guidance for the student of the Sports Talent High School is to take into account every thought, expression, acceptance of the young athlete, establishing vocational, psychological, and psychopedagogical tests with functional tools and continuous dependence on the coach to achieve the proposed sports objectives.

Discussion

A notorious reality, an updated counselor generates potential confidence in the students, which represents the institution. This urges all counselors to seek ways to update their knowledge in various ways and to the extent of their possibilities.

Individual differences	
Reality found	Final discussion
The counselor should employ other orientational techniques that assist the young athlete in deciding on their professional and athletic future, where they discover qualities, skills, interests in sports, limitations, compensations, and opportunities. In other words, analyzing how compatible they are with the objectives they set and what possibilities they have for success.	It is necessary for individuals accompanying the student in their academic and athletic preparation to take into account their individual differences in order to consolidate a positive career choice for them.
The sports coach has a high degree of commitment to the student athlete, as they must motivate, stimulate, and assess the athletic abilities so that the young individual can achieve favorable outcomes within the Vocational Guidance process. It represents the entire personal development, as a maturation process during their life cycle; therefore, mature vocational behavior depends on the evolutionary stage in which they find themselves.	It is crucial for the sports coach to possess the appropriate profile to support the young athlete and provide the student with the necessary tools to consolidate their athletic abilities and potentials, which they will develop during the Vocational Guidance process.

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Individual differences	
Reality found	Final discussion
<p>There is a need for the updating of methodology, techniques, and sports check-ups to meet the demands of young people today, as adolescence brings about various changes, including self-concept, and the young person tends to lean more towards certain activities than others, and the path they embark on is quite extensive.</p>	<p>The teachers must be in constant preparation and updating to provide innovative methodology to the student athlete in their academic and sports preparation.</p>
<p>From the author's perspective, each diagnosis made by the academic instructor should be aligned with the coach's findings; since the primary objective is to reinforce the student both academically and athletically to address the aspirations of each athlete, despite prevalent factors that may disrupt the planning employed.</p>	<p>The sports coach and the academic instructor must be in concurrence to provide the student with the requisite information to enhance the athletic discipline they engage in.</p>

Source: Albis

Conclusions

Orientation becomes collaborative action that enhances innovation and research in educational institutions in an integrated manner within the curriculum and the organizations of the centers. Observing the positive and dynamic conception of the role of a counselor in this society where alarming symptoms of apathy and passivity arise in some young people immersed in a culture of leisure and lack of effort due to crises in family, social, and traditional values, it is important for academic teachers to receive updates in pedagogical tools and thus devote a clear orientation to young people to meet today's demands, taking into consideration each diagnosis made, which must coincide with the discovery made by the coach because the primary objective is to strengthen the student in academic and sports aspects, with the parent or guardian adhering to the guidelines provided by the sports

school and not omitting the recruitment processes. In this context, the orientation model should go beyond the figure of the educational counselor or bodies such as the Guidance Office to become an authentic collaboration process between these and other education professionals in the context of an educational institution, with the intervention object being both the individual, through the work of the academic teacher-coach and tutorial action, including the social and organizational context of learning, i.e., the educational institution itself. Along the same lines, there must be a high level of integration between the institutional collective and sports coaches to carry out the mission and objective that can revitalize affective and effective communication towards the director and vice versa to not lose sight of what is wanted for the young athlete; making the most of links with sports entities for annual changes in sports recruitment processes and high-level methodologies. Ultimately, the future of Educational Guidance in our society lies in constant work without abandoning it, unifying criteria because education to be a true tool of transformation, must be of quality with a functioning public system, with a participative school community, and a sufficient, qualified, and well-remunerated educational staff.

Recommendations

- The role of vocational guidance is of paramount importance, harmoniously linking psychological, pedagogical, and socio-economic capacities with professional, social, and personal development.
- Institutions need to establish the functions of guidance counselors on a firmer basis and align their services with the program's objectives.
- It is the responsibility of the counselor to make the student understand that their decision is personal and that the variables involved are different for each individual, what may be a mistake for one person could be a success for another.

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